

Community Behaviour and Support towards Island Tourism Development

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Abstract—The tourism industry has been widely used to eradicate poverty, due to the ability to generate income, employment as well as improving the quality of life. The industry has faced rapid growth with support from local residents who were involved directly and indirectly in tourism activities. Their support and behaviour does not only facilitate in boosting tourists' satisfaction levels, but at the same time it contributes to the word-of-mouth promotion among the visitors. In order to ensure the success of the industry, the involvement and participation of the local communities are pertinent. This paper endeavours on local community attitudes, benefit and their support toward future tourism development in Tioman Island. Through a series of descriptive and factor analyses, various useful understandings on the issues of interest revealed. The findings indicated that community with personal benefit will support future development. Meanwhile, the finding also revealed that the community with negative perception still supports future tourism development due to their over reliance on this sector as their main source of income and destination development means.

Keywords—Personal benefit, perceived impact, future attitudes.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE growth of the tourism industry is significant to the economic expansion as well as the related industry, such as transportation, leisure services and hospitality. Tourism acknowledged as one of the major attributes for cultural and economic nowadays, especially in moulding the economic composition of a destination. Income generation, currency exchanges and employment opportunity were few of the vast abilities of the tourism industry benefitting a destination [1]. Many small and developing country utilized tourism industry for economic stimulation purposes with the focus on local communities' welfare [2].

Research on tourism development should take into consideration on the roles of personal benefit in tourism development [4]. Currently, the number of studies on local community attitudes towards future tourism development is increasing due to the importance of developmental appropriateness for specific communities and destination [3]. However, little research embarked on the influence of personal benefit from tourism towards their support on tourism development in the future.

Tioman Island is the largest island off the South-East Coast of Malaysia. In 2011, the number of tourist arrivals reached 126,660 tourists domestically as well as internationally. This

is the increasing of 8% in 2010 which recorded the number of tourists is 113,158 [5]. Currently, the economy of the island is supported by agriculture, fishing and village cultivation activities involving near 80% of the total population [6]. The rest of them embarked in tourism businesses providing limited units of chalets and basic tourist services primarily in the provision of food and drinks, hiring of boats, package tours and snorkelling trips [5].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Local communities, mostly known as 'service suppliers' as well as a focal point to cater the accommodation, information, transformation, facilities and services in small tourism destination [7]. Basically, the definition of community is about sharing the boundaries with other people. In addition, local community is a group of individuals living or working within the same geographic of residence. Therefore, it is essential to understand how community development is linked with the ability to boost tourism development [8].

Local community plays their role in influencing the tourism development activities through organizing themselves at all levels to function more effectively with the tourism businesses and policy maker. The success of tourism industry in a small economy relies heavily on the local community support in order to ensure they can gain the positive benefit from tourism development [9]. The local community plays the pivotal roles to members by promoting their physical, social, emotional and mental well being [10]. As suggested from previous literatures, the communities must also work closely with the government organizations to educate the people on the direct and indirect impact of tourism development towards their future lifestyle.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) has been widely accepted as an appropriate framework for analysing local residents' perception and attitudes toward tourism development [11]. The theory encompasses three focal points; economics, environmental, and socio cultural that can assist in determining how residents will respond towards future tourism development [12]. The theory also suggests that communities were expected to engage in an exchange if they believe that the benefit exceed the cost. In terms of tourism industry, residents who perceived tourism to be personally valuable and believe that the cost associated with tourism does not exceed the benefit are expected to support tourism development [11].

The importance of gaining local community support for the tourism development has been discussed thoroughly by tourism scholars as a critical component in achieving successful tourism industry. Support for future tourism

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development is an essential element in developing and implementing successful strategic initiatives [11]. Most of the tourism literatures argued that resident's perception is varied and inconsistent. Some residents view tourism as having both; positive and negative impacts, some are likely to perceive tourism as having negative social and cultural impacts and some are inclined to view tourism as having positive economic, social and cultural impacts. As stated in Social Exchange Theory, if the residents' believe that tourism creates more benefits than cost for the community they will tend to be favourable with tourism and as a result, they will support future development. However, if they believe that tourism brings more damage than benefit, they are not likely to endorse tourism development [12].

Previous researchers mostly assessed the residents' attitudes based on the level of tourism development and institute that residents' attitudes become less positive as the degree of development bullish [12], [13]. They also summarized that residents' initial attitudes towards tourism were enthusiastic but as the cost outweighed benefit of tourism development, attitudes achieve a threshold after which residents support for tourism declined. However, communities with low tourism and bearish economic activity favour tourism development rather than communities with low tourism and high economic activity and communities with high tourism development and low economic activity [13].

III. METHOD

The population of this research is the local community in Tioman Island. There are five villages on this island which are Kampung Salang, Kampung Tekek, Kampung Air Batang, Kampung Paya Genting, Kampung Mukat and Kampung Juara. In 2011, the total number of local communities in Tioman Island is 3314 residents. The number of the population was obtained from the Tioman Development Authority census report.

In order to achieve 95% of confidence level and 5% sampling error, sample size of 248 respondents was determined based on the sample size calculation [14]. The sample included the local community from five different villages on Tioman Island. The sample of the local community was being selected using the quota sampling method to represent the whole local community in Tioman Island. Variables were adapted from previous literature tested in various settings of tourism area and destination [15], [16].

The number of questionnaires distributed is 250 with 229 responses received. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted to determine the links between the observed indicators for unknown or irregular construct. Since the measurement scale in this study was recently measured and quite exploratory in nature, the determination of how and to what extent the observed indicators are linked to the construct of the destination competitive strategy was required. Typically, the principal factors derived from EFA are represented as correlations between sets of various interrelated variables [17].

The results of varimax rotation were reported so that the extracted factors were independent and not correlated with each other. The sample size (N=229) was vigorous enough for exploratory factor analysis [24]. A total of 23 items forming four different factors was utilized from the factor analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was 0.74 conforming the partial correlations among variables are adequate. Basically, these examinations confirmed that since the initial analysis was sufficient, further factor analysis was possible.

TABLE I
FACTOR ANALYSIS MODEL

Factor 1: Personal Benefit	Factor loading
I generate extra income from the tourism industry	.77
I personally feel secure in my current job	.71
I am getting the extra facilities resulted from the tourism industry	.69
I get the best condition of the environment (Air, water & land)	.59
I enjoy the recreation opportunity available	.55
I personally benefit from current tourism development in Tioman Island	.54
<i>Eigen-value</i>	9.16
<i>% of variance explained</i>	27.8
<i>Cumulative %</i>	27.8
<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	.81
Factor 2: Perceived Positive Impact	Factor loading
Improves the local economy and standard of living	.81
Shopping, restaurants and entertainment option is better as a result of tourism	.79
Encourages more public development (road, public facilities)	.78
Provides desirable jobs for local homeowners	.69
Provides incentives for the protection and conservation of natural resources	.57
<i>Eigen-value</i>	4.01
<i>% of variance explained</i>	12.3
<i>Cumulative %</i>	40.1
<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	.80
Factor 3: Perceived Negative Impact	Factor loading
Cost of living increases because of the tourism activity	.71
Overcrowding problem	.67
Increasing litter problem	.64
Lead to friction between community and tourist	.60
Increasing number of crimes	.55
<i>Eigen-value</i>	2.10
<i>% of variance explained</i>	6.5
<i>Cumulative %</i>	46.6
<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	.71
Factor 4: Support for tourism development	Factor loading
I believe that the tourism industry should be actively encouraged in my community	.81
I support tourism and would like to see it become important part of my community	.77
I will support new tourism facilities that will attract more tourism in my community	.65
I believe tourism should be actively encouraged in Tioman Island	.58
I believe the tourism sector will continue to play a major role in the economy of the community	.56
<i>Eigen-value</i>	1.59
<i>% of variance explained</i>	4.9
<i>Cumulative %</i>	51.5
<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	.75
<i>Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin =</i>	0.74

IV. ANALYSIS

From the total of 229 respondents, the age range of respondents was between 45 years old to 54 years old represent 31.7% of total respondent followed by a range between 35 years old to 44 years old with 27.6%. The respondents are made up of 56.7% males and 44.3% females. The majority of respondents were married (88.3%). Most of the respondents hold primary and secondary level education. 42.8% of them are working in the tourism industry related jobs such as employee in the chalet, resort or handicraft shops, became tourist guide, boatman as well as operating the scuba diving shop. There were 97 respondents working as part timers with the earning between RM700 – RM1,000.

Majority of respondents' reported gaining the benefits of tourism development in Tioman Island. Safety and security, job creation and social life were identified as three major perspectives on community personal benefit from tourism development. This result is consistent with the establishment of police booth at every village in Tioman Island in order to control and coordinate the safety and security purposes especially for both local communities and tourists as well. Generally, the increasing number of tourist influx in Tioman Island had improved the local community economy activities.

However, the majority of the respondents' perceived that tourism development resulted in higher cost of living. This is in line with previous studies which identified tourism activity extremely correlate with the high cost of living [18]. Further, while the declaration of the duty free zone boosted up the arrival of tourists, however, the local communities feel inconvenient with the overcrowding issues. Furthermore, frictions between tourist and local community, as well as crime resulted from the tourism activities were recorded. However, the majority of respondents believed that the tourism sector will continue to play a crucial role towards prospering the economy of Tioman Island. This is quite a startling result, signalling that the local communities were too reliant on the tourism industry as their main source of earnings [19].

V. HIERARCHICAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Moderated regression analysis, as the recommended method for testing interaction effects, was applied. Hierarchical multiple regression analyses were performed to detect main effects and interaction effects [20]. The hypothesis on perceived positive impact moderates the relationship between personal benefit from tourism development and support for future tourism development was accepted based on the regression result ($Adj. R^2 = 0.452$, $F = 7.253$, $p < 0.001$). The main effects of the independent variables and the moderator variable of perceived positive impact were found significance based on the noteworthy change of R^2 value. The result is in line with many researchers who identified that residents' who are dependent on tourism industry, favouring economic gain or have personal benefit tend to be more supportive towards tourism development [11], [15], [16], [21].

TABLE II
MEAN SCORE ON DESCRIPTIVE STATEMENT

No	Personal Benefit from Tourism Development	N	Mean	Std deviation
1	I generate extra income from the tourism industry	229	4.15	.761
2	I personally feel assured of my current job	229	4.31	.716
3	I am getting the extra facilities resulted from the tourism industry	229	4.50	.575
4	I get the best condition of the environment (air, water & land)	229	3.20	.564
5	I enjoy the recreation opportunity available	229	3.90	.772
6	I personally benefited from current tourism development in Tioman Island	229	4.32	.901
Perceived Positive Impact				
1	Improves the local economy and standard of living	229	3.82	.762
2	Shopping, restaurants and entertainment option is better as a result of tourism	229	4.42	.681
3	Encourages more public development (road, public facilities)	229	4.49	.574
4	Provides desirable jobs for local homeowners	229	4.10	.900
5	Provides incentives for the protection and conservation of natural resources	229	4.07	.717
Perceived Negative Impacts				
1	Cost of living increases because of the tourism activity	229	3.37	.649
2	Overcrowding problem	229	3.18	.406
3	Increasing litter problem	229	3.06	.345
4	Lead to friction between community and tourist	229	2.74	.253
Support for Future Tourism Development				
1	I believe that the tourism industry should be actively encouraged in my community	229	4.73	.896
2	I support tourism and would like to see it become an important part of my community	229	4.67	.520
3	I will support new tourism facilities that will attract more tourism in my community	229	4.63	.546
4	I believe tourism should be actively encouraged in Tioman Island	229	4.58	.541
5	I believe the tourism sector will continue to play a major role in the economy of the community	229	4.73	.746

TABLE III
PERCEIVED POSITIVE IMPACT MODERATION EFFECT

Independent Variables	Before moderation		After moderation	
	Beta	t-statistic	Beta	t-statistic
Model 1 : Perceived positive impact moderates the relationship between personal benefit from tourism development and support for future tourism development				
Model statistics				
Personal benefit from tourism development	.656***	6.390	.597***	7.201
Perceived positive impact			.451***	5.178
		Adj R-square = .435	Adj R-square = .452	
		F = 7.182	F = 7.253	
		p = .00	p = .00	

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.01$

The hypothesis on perceived negative impact moderates the relationship between personal benefit from tourism development and support for future tourism development was somewhat accepted based on the regression result ($Adj. R^2 =$

0.24, $F = 6.412$, $p < 0.001$). The main effects of the independent variables and the moderator variable of perceived positive impact were found significance based on the notable change of R^2 value. This result was contradictory with previous researches [21]-[23] but consistent with studies by [12]. Even though the respondents were not in favour of tourism development, however, their over reliance on tourism as their main income generator lead them to support tourism development in the future.

TABLE IV
PERCEIVED NEGATIVE IMPACT MODERATION EFFECT

Independent Variables	Before moderation		After moderation	
	Beta	t-statistic	Beta	t-statistic
Model 2 : Perceived negative impact moderates the relationship between personal benefit from tourism development and support for future tourism development				
Model statistics				
Personal benefit from tourism development	.192***	4.390	.145**	4.178
Perceived negative impact			.247**	4.874
	Adj R-square = .25 F = 6.841 p = .00		Adj R-square = .24 F = 6.412 p = .00	

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

VI. CONCLUSION

The result of this study clearly shows that community with personal economic benefit will definitely promote tourism development. Personal benefits had been identified as a striking aspect associated with the future attitudes towards tourism development. Furthermore, the outcome of this study shows that community resistance against tourism development is based on their negative perception from tourism development. Local community who personally benefited from tourism development will be more supportive towards future development. Thus, tourism businesses and policy maker should be responsive to these issues. The practice of preservation activities and on-going information dissemination might alleviate the negative issues. Moreover, tourism organisations should ensure that the communities are involved directly in the planning and development process and ensure future tourism development should create more benefits than costs for the community. If the policy maker is able to offer benefits from tourism activities, the more support is likely will be from the local communities.

Future researchers should investigate other aspects that may affect community support for tourism development, such as level of involvement, economy size, and level of community attachment. The assimilation of these dimensions into a structural model will further grasp the factors that affect residents support for tourism development. In addition, future researchers should continue to test and validate the role of personal benefit from tourism development towards support for future tourism development in different communities and other tourism destinations.

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